

Abstract

This paper assumes an increase in the total Canadian government spending towards natural resource extraction projects of all sizes and uses environmental economics to compare projects. This paper starts with an example from oil and gas in BC, where producers flare waste methane gas that could otherwise be captured to reduce pollution and increase commercial value. This article considers a scenario where the government starts a new policy for minimum standards of waste gas capture, then the government pays to build the methane capture circuits for the companies if they don't do it themselves. If the government pays for the methane capture and the company gets a free boost in revenue, then there may be some partial tax liability; for example, a tax liability that can be paid in-kind by doing environmental beneficiation somewhere in BC. This paper also considers an example in Saskatchewan, where an estimate for the capital cost of "enhanced oil recovery" is used to generate a model for military spending on oil and gas with estimates for the GDP multiplier. Based on the way the government is directly involved at the operational level in these scenarios, the paper also raises the idea of government insurance for industrial disasters and government investment into bottlenecks for supply chains of strategic significance.

Keywords: GDP, Canada, BC, Saskatchewan, Oil, Gas, Methane, Environmental, Military

JEL Codes:

B5 - Current Heterodox Approaches	H57 - Procurement
C60 - General	K2 - Regulation and Business Law
C8 - Data Collection and Data Estimation	K23 - Regulated Industries and Administrative Law
Methodology Computer Programs	L3 - Nonprofit Organizations and Public Enterprise
C81 - Methodology for Collecting, Estimating, and	L32 - Public Enterprises ; Public-Private Enterprises
Organizing Microeconomic Data; Data Access	L5 - Regulation and Industrial Policy
D2 - Production and Organizations	L7 - Industry Studies: Primary Products and
D7 - Production and Organizations	Construction
E0 - General	L72 - Mining, Extraction, and Refining: Other
E01 - Measurement and Data on National Income and	Nonrenewable Resources
Product Accounts and Wealth; Environmental Accounts	N5 - Agriculture, Natural Resources, Environment,
E6 - Policy Objectives ; Policy Designs and	O1 - Economic Development
Consistency ; Policy Coordination	O13 - Agriculture ; Natural Resources ; Energy ;
F3 - International Finance	Environment ; Other Primary Products
G1 - General Financial Markets	O2 - Development Planning and Policy
G17 - Financial Forecasting and Simulation	P1 - Capitalist Systems
H1 - Structure and Scope of Government	Q3 - Nonrenewable Resources and Conservation
H2 - Taxation, Subsidies, and Revenue	Q32 - Exhaustible Resources and Economic
H5 - National Government Expenditures and Policy	Development
H54 - Infrastructures, Other Public Investment, and	Q33 - Resource Booms
Capital Stock	Q5 - Environmental Economics
	Y1 - Data: Tables and Charts

Military Spending on Domestic Oil and Gas Production in Canada

This paper assumes an increase in the total Canadian government spending towards natural resource extraction projects of all sizes and uses environmental economics to compare projects. This paper starts with an example from oil and gas in BC, where producers flare waste methane gas that could otherwise be captured to reduce pollution and increase commercial value. This article considers a scenario where the government starts a new policy for minimum standards of waste gas capture, then the government pays to build the methane capture circuits for the companies if they don't do it themselves. If the government pays for the methane capture and the company gets a free boost in revenue, then there may be some partial tax liability; for example, a tax liability that can be paid in-kind by doing environmental beneficiation somewhere in BC. This paper also considers an example in Saskatchewan, where an estimate for the capital cost of "enhanced oil recovery" is used to generate a model for military spending on oil and gas with estimates for the GDP multiplier. Based on the way the government is directly involved at the operational level in these scenarios, the paper also raises the idea of government insurance for industrial disasters and government investment into bottlenecks for supply chains of strategic significance.

Government Action on Methane Capture in BC

The Canadian Climate Institute (2025b) article notes, *"In fact, Canada's oil and gas sector has already made substantial progress in cutting methane emissions roughly in half over the past decade. In addition, many Canadian companies are already leaders in methane detection and mitigation."* Canada's leadership reflects a relative advantage in methane capture versus oil and gas producers globally. Government spending can focus on things that the domestic industry is already doing well to press our advantage, or the government can help the laggards domestically match the best actors in the domestic Canadian industry. These are examples of how we can compare government spending in terms of whether it targets the best or worst actors in a business niche. We can also compare government spending as to whether it generates any economic windfall and who captures the economic rents.

Imagine a scenario where the government pays for methane capture programs for all oil and gas producers in BC on a subsidized basis. This article assumes the government implements this change in two phases: it starts with a new policy for minimum standards of methane capture by the industry, then the government offers a free program to build the methane capture circuits for producers in BC to meet the new minimums or lets the companies do it themselves. If producers already capture methane themselves, then they don't need the government at their site. But if a company cannot do it themselves, then the government builds it for them at their site for free. This government program could require companies who get free methane capture to match their spending on environmental beneficiation projects in BC elsewhere to offset the economic rents they capture from the government spending. For example, half of the additional revenue to the company could be spent towards environmental remediation projects on an in-kind basis, where the company does environmental beneficiation projects in BC.

This unusual approach to government spending has a few effects. There may be negative impacts for the companies that have to deal with the government operating a methane recovery circuit at their site, which incentivizes companies to do it themselves. In contrast, companies have incentives to let the government do it for them and collect the additional revenue for free. This type of government spending is similar to other types of brute-force government spending to force companies to start doing more methane capture, like if the government gives companies cash funding to build it themselves.

By designing the government program to fund methane capture across the province for all oil and gas producers, this policy is meant to press our advantage. We are already good at methane capture, as mentioned in the Canadian Climate Institute (2025b) article, so this type of government policy and funding is meant to incentivize all the companies to get better at what we are already good at doing. This policy approach assumes the government has vigorous enforcement of the new policy for minimum standards, and the government is able to fund and execute the plan to build the methane capture facilities at existing operations owned and operated by industry in BC. Government credibility is essential here and highlights the need for functionality beyond the current capabilities of the BC government.

One way for the BC government to function beyond its own current capabilities is to work with the Canadian military on an operational basis. The military may not yet have these capabilities itself, but this paper assumes it is a federal government priority to create new military operational capacity to support domestic natural resource production and infrastructure. The military represents an exogenous source of spending relative to the BC economy, which has direct and indirect impacts. I further assume that the military only uses materials from Canadian sources, which causes additional GDP multipliers. The rationale for military involvement here is to focus on the security of supply for the domestic industry, rather than profitability.

This thought experiment assumes the military pays for and executes the build-out of methane capture facilities at all projects in the province for free to the company; unless the company does it themselves, then the military does it for them. There may be costs for this policy, such as negative, crowding-out effects on other businesses in Canada. There may be several benefits from this policy. For example, it may force the government to create new institutional capabilities to support strategic domestic industries. For another example, military involvement in domestic supply chains may give better information about potential bottlenecks for supplies of critical materials and allow the military to start playing a more active role to improve the security of supply.

This article starts with military involvement in basic commerce, but it can be extended to consider scenarios where the military spending is meant to support procurement for Canada and allied countries. It can also be extended to consider insurance. By getting involved at the operational level with businesses, the government gathers more information about industry risks, which could lead to financial innovation with new insurance products or reinsurance markets.

This spending entails a tremendous cost to the government because the government currently does not operate small natural gas businesses with local owners, and there may be high costs to build a government institution that can execute this plan. The institutional costs for the government to set up the capabilities to build these capture facilities could be larger than the costs of the facilities themselves because the government does not currently do this type of work.

Military Spending on Enhanced Oil Recovery in Saskatchewan

The example Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) in Saskatchewan requires a relatively small number of projects, each with a relatively large cost. A comprehensive article by Navius Research Inc. (2024) gives an estimate for the EOR capital costs of \$42/bbl capex in 2020 for Saskatchewan. It doesn't give an estimate for how many oil reservoirs can be filled with carbon dioxide gas to do EOR or how much new oil and gas production would be caused by EOR, but I assume it applies to all of the 2020 production.

As in the Navius Research report, the capital costs for EOR are \$42/bbl compared with oil prices of \$30-40 CAD at the time. Total Saskatchewan oil production was 0.5 million barrels per day at the time, which is a total revenue of approximately \$20 million per day or approximately \$750 million per year. The costs for EOR are high enough that companies are not doing it currently, but government action could change incentives. This article proposes a brute force approach where the government builds the EOR itself.

Total Saskatchewan GDP is \$70-80 billion, and the total costs of EOR of \$0.8 billion represent approximately 1% of GDP. The total provincial government budget in 2020 was around \$16 billion, and the EOR would cost around 4%. How do these amounts compare with other types of government spending, like the military? The Canadian military targets an increase of \$20 billion per year to reach the NATO target, so the total EOR costs represent 4% of the total increase in military funding.

However, the cost for the military to create the ability to do the EOR work itself would be an additional amount. It may cost the military more than two times as much to build the institutional infrastructure to build, deploy, and monitor the EOR facilities because it does not currently do this type of work. The total cost of EOR is approximately \$0.8 billion per year, and there may be another \$2 billion in new military spending required for the military to be able to do the EOR work only using materials and people sourced in Canada.

The military can have several impacts by developing this industry expertise in the oil and gas business domestically. For one, it can have potential economic multipliers on GDP. For another, the military can develop some vertical integration for procurement by developing new industrial capabilities. This procurement discussion can be expanded to broader questions, like whether it would be possible for the Canadian military to only use Canadian oil in operations around the world. This degree of integration could be impractical or prohibitively expensive, but it is not a profit-motivated decision because it can benefit national security in terms of security of supply.

There are several types of economic multipliers for EOR spending. The capital costs for EOR are approximately \$0.8 billion per year for all oil production in Saskatchewan, and there are additional costs for the military to build capabilities to do the EOR work themselves of approximately \$2 billion per year. There are additional direct and indirect impacts from this EOR program as follows. A list of GDP impacts is below:

- 1, EOR capital costs are \$0.8 billion.
2. Military costs to do the EOR work are \$2 billion.
3. Value of new primary production is \$0.8 billion.
- 4, Indirect impacts of increased oil, EOR costs, and military spending are \$1 billion.
- 5, The theoretical value of carbon offsets is \$0.4 billion.
- 6, Potential increase in oil and gas production from all the EOR is \$0.6 billion.

The total GDP impacts are approximately \$5 billion per year. In comparison, the direct military spending costs are assumed to be \$2.8 billion, which gives a multiplier of less than 2x for military spending in this model.

The military is targeting an increase in total spending of \$20 billion per year to reach NATO targets, and this \$2.8 billion cost would represent 14% of new military spending. This is a massive commitment for something that the military is not doing at all right now. Although it is outside the focus of the Canadian military today, this type of expertise could be helpful for the Canadian military on a global basis in terms of relative advantage for military procurement.

This paper does not capture potential revenue generation from EOR activities. This may generate profits, but they are not large enough to motivate businesses to do EOR themselves now and would not be the main reason for the military to fund this activity. If the current total value of oil production is \$0.8 billion in 2020 and we do EOR for all of it, then it could generate an additional \$0.6 billion in oil production. There could be economic multipliers from direct and indirect effects for this new primary production of oil and gas from the EOR.

The Canadian military may not currently analyze the cost of pollution from its operations. For example, how much carbon pollution is created by the military across all activities globally? If the military funds EOR, then it is possible to use carbon capture from EOR to offset the pollution from military activities. The Canadian military could achieve carbon offset goals while investing in domestic natural resources and increasing security of supply. Also, there is a potential commercial value for the carbon credits created by EOR that the military can sell in global markets. It may be possible for the Canadian military to start providing other allied militaries with carbon credits for their operations based on carbon sequestration from EOR in Saskatchewan.

Military spending on the oil industry in Saskatchewan may seem inappropriate because it is currently not done, but the natural resource endowment of Canada provides many opportunities for the Canadian military to develop expertise in natural resources in ways that improve military readiness. This government spending can generate new oil production that is used for procurement by Canada or allied militaries to create more security of supply for Canadian critical materials.

Opportunities with Alberta, Critical Minerals, and more

The methodology used here can be applied to other settings. For example, the Canadian Climate Institute (2025a) report on critical minerals provides a recommendation for “Improved financial assurance for mine closures.” The report does not give an estimate for total spending on that item, but total costs across Canada could range from \$0.1 billion to \$2 billion or more. The

government could spend a billion dollars a year cleaning up old mine sites and monitoring ongoing operations for potential mine site disaster risk.

Consider the example of the Victoria Gold Corp mine disaster in the Yukon in 2024. What if the military were involved at the mine site during operations with a dedicated focus on geotechnical risk assessments from the start of production? This mine was the first time a valley-fill, open-pit mine was built in Canada on the scale of a mega project, so there was always technical uncertainty about the geotechnical risks. The government ended up with the liabilities after the mine disaster *ex post*; could it reduce the damage by getting involved *a priori* before the disaster? As governments get more involved on an operational basis, there is a potential for the government to get involved in new types of insurance for natural resource extraction industries. Also, the government can target their spending towards operational risks based on firsthand knowledge about shortcomings within industry.

There are opportunities for the Canadian government to get more involved in the natural resources industries in Alberta, too. The government can tackle projects that may not be profitable enough to motivate individual businesses to act on them. Government spending may create new domestic business ecosystems driven by new demand from military procurement, or spending may create new sources of supply using Canadian people and products that causes business development into new areas that are currently avoided. In this way, government spending can improve security of supply for strategic materials by brute-force methods where the government starts making the missing products or services, or by using government to induce businesses to start filling a gap in markets. This paper explores strategic materials like oil and gas, but these ideas can be extended to farming; the military needs to feed many people, so it may start getting involved in food production to help ensure the security of supply for mission-critical items like specialized military rations.

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